

Study of quenched Er³⁺-ions in the high-power regime at CW and pulse pumping configurations

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ABSTRACT

Fiber laser sources, in particular in amplifier configurations, offer very appealing attractions such as high efficiency, compact and low cost. Erbium-doped fibers are attractive for their wavelength range (1520 – 1610 nm), but suffer from quenching through energy-transfer upconversion (ETU) at high doping concentrations¹. The effect of quenched ions is studied in the high-power regime and the comparison between its behaviour in CW and pulse pumping configurations leads to a possible solution for this limitation.

Key words: Fiber laser, Erbium-doped fiber, concentration quenching, pulse pumping.

1. INTRODUCTION

The field of fiber lasers was born in 1961, its numerous advantages are established fabrication procedures, low loss, and the possibility of pumping with compact, efficient diode lasers. The fiber itself provides the waveguide, and the availability of various fiber components minimizes the need for bulk optics and mechanical alignment.

Fiber lasers need to be pumped optically, and thus, the properties of the pump sources are crucial for high power fiber lasers. Practical fiber lasers typically depend on diode lasers for pumping. The power produced by fiber lasers is restricted by the amount of pump light coupled into them. The main pump sources discussed in this paper are the continuous wave (CW) laser and the pulsed laser.

There has always been the need to reach higher power, and while there have been many improvements over the years, there are still strong limitations that comes with the use of optical fibers. In order to cope with the need for high power fiber lasers, higher doping concentration is required to maintain sufficient pump absorption along the fiber, which may lead to photodarkening and concentration quenching effects (depending of the rare-earth dopant), inducing excessive optical losses. To solve these issues, the system could rely on longer fibers, diminishing the detrimental effects of quenching. However, longer fibers could lead to unwanted optical nonlinear effects due to tightly confined waveguide mode. This issue can be solve by

the use of a short fiber. The problem lies in the fact that you cannot use a long and a short fiber at the same time.

As a possible way to solve this challenge, this paper shows an investigation of pumping with high-energy pulses of durations considerably shorter than the pulse period. Pump pulse durations may be in the range of 100 ns to tens of microseconds, with pulse energy ultimately on the μ J-level or higher. This translates to pump peak powers of 100 W. This paper focuses on an architecture known as tandem-pumping [2], which consists of a signal gain fiber pumped by a fiber laser configured to generate high-energy pump pulses with peak powers.

Erbium-doped fiber (EDF) is the main focus on this paper. A reason to work with EDF is that the concentration quenching is expected to be constant in time, as well as having an interesting wavelength with a larger field of application, in the sensor or communication industries.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DEVELOPMENTS

2.1. Pump pulse source and signal fiber amplifier

the project depends on two different and very important stages, refer to as pump pulse source and the signal pulse amplification. The overall system require of three imperative components: Pump pulse generator, signal ‘seed’ pulse laser and the signal fiber amplifier.

To maximize the performance of the pulsed lasers, a judicious selection of pulse duration and repetition rate is required. there are two pulsed lasers involve:

The pump pulse, which generates high-energy pulses that are later going to be absorbed by the signal fiber amplifier. The second is the signal ‘seed’ pulse laser, in charge of sending signal pulses that are going to be amplified by extracting the energy stored by the high-energy pump pulses in the signal fiber amplifier.

2.2 Core pumping

Core pumping has the advantage of working at short fiber lengths, which leads to lower optical nonlinearities. However, assuming that the core area from the pump fiber and the signal fiber amplifier are equals, the saturation energy in the signal wavelength will always be higher than at the pump wavelength. Therefore, the limited pump energy sets an upper limit on the signal energy.

2.3 Limitations

In the context of obtaining high energy and power, there are limitations in the performance of a rare-earth doped fiber. For this project, the main limitations are energy-transfer upconversion and optical nonlinearities.

The energy-transfer upconversion (ETU) is the phenomenon that dopant ions in laser-active media can exchange excitation energy among each other. This effect happens too frequently in highly doped fiber and particularly when clustering of ions occurs (this is called concentration quenching) which Er-ions tend to do. If the upper laser level for some laser transition is quenched, the upper-state lifetime is reduced, raising the threshold pump power of the EDF laser and reduce the gain of the signal fiber amplifier [14]. This process is illustrated in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Graphic explanation behind ETU.

The ETU is estimated to have a timescale of 1 – 10 μ s, also demonstrated by measurements of the fluorescence lifetime on highly doped EDF (assuming concentrations higher than $1E+26$ ions / m^3).

In the modern-state-of-the-art, it is recommended to simply use a low concentration EDF and increasing the fiber length to compensate for the lack of power.

However, this leads to large nonlinear distortions building up along the fiber in the high power regime, which strongly reduces the efficiency of the amplifier.

2.4 Simulations and experimental results

Through the use of the software RP FiberPower, it was possibly to run simulations by controlling the percentage of ions undergoing concentration quenching and subsequent ETU. Under the same condition, with the only difference being the pump source, the use of pulse pumping (with pulse duration below the timescale of the ETU) proved to remain unaffected by high concentration quenching, as shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2: Output power vs Er³⁺-cluster

2.5 Conclusions

It is clear that this method may lead to overcome the disadvantage of concentration quenching, at the end, it should be noted that the signal fiber amplifier through pulse pumping could surpass other conventional CW amplifiers by avoiding ETU as well as other nonlinear effects that build up along the fiber length.

2.6 References

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